

Coordinate Descent for the Learning Rate and Weight Update Mask Size of Blind Descent

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Abstract

Blind Descent achieves about 73 percent accuracy for MNIST data. The proposed hypothesis as to why there is error remaining is that the Gaussian random distribution works like a uniform random distribution for small learning rate (as defined in that paper). So, assume we have to update only one weight. We have the freedom to choose a learning rate for that update which results in "ideal" model if we repeat it for all weights. But, training it for each weight individually and independently with Blind Descent is computationally expensive as we have to do inference once for each update. Hence, a mask based training is being proposed.

Note: I am planning to discuss the experiments' results using the peer reviewed version of this. As of now, I haven't discussed any experimental results of the proposed algorithm. All experiments may be run using CNN, MNIST and CPU.

1 Introduction

One of the main reasons why this research papers is being authored is because of the practical experimental proof that is needed for the Blind Descent algorithm for it to be used as widely as backpropagation. Also, given that not all weights have to have a uniform random distribution for a weight vector update, this research is about statistics of mask size. Coordinate descent is being used for the hyperparameter tuning. The hyperparameters are learning rate and the mask size. Note that the mask size is a scalar and this research is about proposing that this idea works and is the missing piece of the puzzle of Blind Descent.

2 Prior Work

Blind Descent is the core algorithm of this.[1] Coordinate Descent is a simple enough algorithm that practically works for multiple types of convex optimisation problems.[2] So, this is being used for two hyperparameters: learning rate and weight update mask size. For the learning rate, binary search optimiser may work for Blind Descent also.[3]

3 Proposed algorithm

The coordinate descent is between weight update mask size and the learning rate. The learning rate is supposed to be selected using binary search. The mask size is supposed to be selected using the following sub-algorithm:

- Initial mask size power $M = M_{max} = \lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor$
where N is the number of parameters in the network.
- Get the weight update matrices using the learning rate sub-algorithm (using binary search).
- Select 2^M pseudo-random weights that we need to update (and the corresponding weight updates from weight update matrices)
- Wait until we get future loss greater than current loss.
- Then, decrease M by 1 until future loss is lesser than current loss. Then, increase M by 1 until future loss is greater than current loss. Then, switch over to learning rate optimisation (coordinate descent)
- At any point $M < 1$, $M = 1$.
(Because, for less than two weights, there is no significant difference between this algorithm and backpropagation)
At any point $M > M_{max}$, $M = M_{Max}$

This can be made easier by doing this layer by layer (instead of complete network all at once).

References

- [1] Akshat Gupta and Prasad N R, “*Blind Descent: A Prequel to Gradient Descent*”, Vol. 783 Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, ICDSMLA, Springer (2020)
- [2] Wright S J, *Coordinate descent algorithms*, Math Program, 151 3-34, Springer (2015)
- [3] Prasad N R, *Binary Search (tree) Non-physics Learning Rate Optimiser*, Zenodo, 6 October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13894972>.